

The protease threshold: a conceptual framework for germinal matrix hemorrhage

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Graphical sketch

Abstract

Germinal matrix hemorrhage (GMH) is a major cause of mortality and long-term neurological disability in preterm infants, yet the mechanism underlying the selective vulnerability of the germinal matrix (GM) remains unclear. The GM is a highly angiogenic, protease-active developmental niche that operates near the limits of vascular stability under tightly regulated intrauterine conditions. Preterm birth disrupts this balance by removing late-gestational immune modulation and exposing protease-primed GM vessels to exaggerated inflammatory activation. Dysregulated innate immune responses amplify endothelial junctional cleavage and basement-membrane degradation and reprogram the local myeloid environment toward neutrophil-derived protease release. We propose a unified protease-threshold framework in which GMH occurs when inflammatory amplification drives proteolytic activity beyond the structural resilience of the immature GM vasculature. This model explains the timing, localization, and heterogeneity of GMH and provides a mechanistic basis for biomarker discovery and preventive strategies.

1. Introduction

Intraventricular hemorrhage (IVH) remains one of the most devastating complications of prematurity and a leading cause of long-term neurological disability, including cerebral palsy, cognitive impairment, and post-hemorrhagic hydrocephalus(1, 2). In preterm infants, IVH almost invariably originates in the germinal matrix (GM), a transient, highly vascularized proliferative zone in the caudothalamic groove that supports rapid neurogenesis and vascular expansion during late gestation(3, 4).

The traditional structural–developmental model attributes GM vulnerability to immature vasculature, sparse pericyte coverage, and high metabolic demand(5, 6). While this framework explains the anatomical localization of hemorrhage, it does not fully account for its timing or

heterogeneity. IVH typically emerges hours to days after birth rather than during delivery, occurs in utero in association with severe chorioamnionitis, and displays striking variability among infants of similar gestational age(4, 7). These observations have led to the recognition of IVH as a multifactorial disorder involving structural, hemodynamic, developmental, and inflammatory influences(8).

Within this landscape, the GM should not be viewed as a passive or inherently fragile structure but as a highly active developmental niche. Its intense angiogenic program—driven by high expression of VEGF and angiopoietin-2—requires continuous endothelial sprouting and extracellular-matrix remodeling(9, 10). These processes depend on a coordinated proteolytic repertoire that includes MMP-9, membrane-type MMPs (e.g., MMP-14), ADAM sheddases, calpains, and cathepsins(10-12). Experimental VEGF overexpression in the GM upregulates these proteases and is sufficient to induce hemorrhage, demonstrating that dysregulated developmental proteolysis alone can destabilize this vascular bed(10, 13). Thus, even under optimal conditions, the GM operates near the limits of structural stability.

Preterm birth abruptly transfers this protease-primed vascular niche from a tightly regulated intrauterine environment to a postnatal setting characterized by hypoxic, microbial, and other inflammatory stimuli. Mounting evidence indicates that the preterm innate immune system responds to these early exposures with exaggerated cytokine and myeloid activation(14-16), altering microglial–vascular trophic interactions and promoting inflammatory amplification at the GM vasculature.(17) How this inflammatory escalation interacts with developmental protease activity to precipitate vascular failure remains incompletely understood.

Here, we propose that IVH arises when inflammatory amplification transiently drives proteolytic activity in the GM beyond the limited structural resilience of its immature vasculature. This protease-threshold framework provides a unified mechanistic explanation for the localization,

timing, and clinical heterogeneity of IVH and establishes a basis for identifying predictive biomarkers and rational preventive strategies.

2. A Unified Mechanism of IVH: Immune–Vascular Disruption and Protease-Threshold Failure.

The pathogenesis of intraventricular hemorrhage (IVH) arises from the pathological convergence of two normal developmental programs that become temporally misaligned by premature birth: (1) protease-dependent vascular remodeling that drives germinal matrix (GM) angiogenesis(10, 18), and (2) innate immune activation triggered by postnatal inflammatory exposures, including microbial ligands, hypoxia–ischemia, metabolic stress, and mechanical respiratory support(14, 15, 19-22). In term infants, these programs unfold sequentially under tight immune moderation; in preterm infants, they collide. The result is transformation of the GM’s physiological proteolytic landscape into a “proteolytic storm”. By proteolytic storm we refer to a transient, self-amplifying convergence of developmental and immune-derived protease activity exceeding physiological control. Evidence for the convergence of developmental protease priming and immune-derived protease amplification in the germinal matrix has emerged from recent human and experimental studies(17, 23). Hemorrhage occurs once this combined proteolytic and inflammatory load exceeds a protease threshold defined by the structural and developmental limits of the immature GM vasculature (*see Figure 1*).

2.1 Pathological Convergence: Developmental Priming Meets Immune Reprogramming and Inflammatory Amplification

A key insight from recent human developmental and GMH tissue studies is that the GM vasculature is not merely immature—it is uniquely immune-dependent. Prenatal microglia and vasculature-associated myeloid cells (VAM) provide trophic, angiogenic, and stabilizing cues that are essential for GM vascular maturation(17). Premature birth acutely disrupts this

immune–vascular partnership and exposes the region to inflammatory stimuli precisely when immune-derived angiogenic support is most critical.

The GM is developmentally primed for proteolysis. Its rapid angiogenic expansion—driven by VEGF and angiopoietin-2—requires continuous extracellular-matrix turnover and junctional remodeling mediated by MMP-9, MT1-MMP (MMP-14), cathepsins, ADAM10, ADAMTS proteases, and intracellular calpains that regulate cytoskeletal and junctional plasticity(11, 24, 25). Under fetal conditions, this proteolytic activity is tightly regulated and spatially confined.

Recent evidence reveals that immune cells orchestrate much of this developmental angiogenesis. Prenatal microglia and vessel-associated macrophages physically associate with nascent GM vessels, promote sprouting and branching, and express endothelial-supportive gene programs(17). Experimental depletion of these cells selectively reduces GM vascular density, demonstrating a region-specific dependence of GM angiogenesis on immune–vascular signaling(17).

Premature birth acts as an abrupt biological “phase shift.” It removes late-gestational immunomodulators(26, 27) and exposes the protease-rich GM vasculature to inflammatory and microbial stimuli at its moment of maximal developmental vulnerability. The preterm innate immune system—hyperreactive and dysregulated—responds excessively to the postnatal inflammatory triggers(14, 15, 22). These stimuli both activate endothelial and extracellular proteases and reprogram immune cells from pro-angiogenic microglia to neutrophil- and monocyte-dominant inflammatory phenotypes(17).

The convergence of developmental priming, inflammatory amplification, and immune-cell reprogramming creates the conditions for vascular failure.

2.2 The Molecular Architecture of the Proteolytic Storm

At the molecular level, this convergence is executed through a coordinated network of intracellular and extracellular proteases(28-30). Among the protease families implicated in germinal matrix (GM) vascular injury, calpains occupy a unique topological position in the cascade: they are directly activated by upstream inflammatory and hypoxic Ca^{2+} signals(31-33), regulate cytoskeletal anchoring of junctional complexes and VE-cadherin stability(34-36), and can potentiate extracellular matrix protease activation(28, 37). While multiple protease families contribute, current evidence positions calpain as a plausible intracellular convergence node linking extracellular inflammatory exposure to endothelial barrier failure.

A central axis of vascular destabilization in preterm GM hemorrhage therefore lies in Ca^{2+} -dependent calpain activation within endothelial cells(31, 32, 38). Inflammatory cytokines, Toll-like receptor (TLR) signaling, hypoxic stress, and metabolic perturbations elevate intracellular Ca^{2+} , directly activating μ - and m-calpain(31, 38). Activated calpains cleave spectrin, talin, and other cytoskeletal anchoring proteins that link VE-cadherin to the actin cytoskeleton, weakening the intracellular scaffold required for adherens-junction stability. Calpain also cleaves cytoplasmic junctional domains, accelerating junctional internalization and loss of cohesion. Through these actions, calpain converts upstream inflammatory and hypoxic stimuli into an intracellular program of barrier destabilization(34, 35, 39).

Calpain activation functionally cooperates with membrane sheddases such as ADAM10, which mediate ectodomain cleavage of VE-cadherin. Microbial TLR4 agonists, hypoxia, oxidative stress, and metabolic disturbances induce ADAM10 activation(40-42) and TLR4 stimulation triggers ADAM10-dependent VE-cadherin cleavage in neonatal brain microvessels, resulting in acute junctional disassembly(17). Hypoxia further amplifies this process through HIF-1 α stabilization and VEGF induction, which upregulate ADAM10 activity and promote junctional destabilization(43-45). Importantly, calpain-mediated disruption of cytoskeletal anchoring

increases VE-cadherin accessibility to ADAM10, accelerating ectodomain shedding and establishing a feed-forward loop of junctional collapse(17).

In parallel, extracellular proteases degrade the vascular basement membrane. Inflammatory and hypoxic stimuli induce secretion of MMP-9, MT1-MMP, and cathepsins B, L, and S, which cleave collagen IV, laminin, nidogen, and perlecan—components already thin and discontinuous in the GM(28, 29, 46). Combined hypoxia and TLR activation markedly increase MMP-9 and MT1-MMP activity in neonatal brain tissue, producing regionally selective basement-membrane breakdown that further destabilizes endothelial junctions and reduces mechanical resistance to hemodynamic stress(17). Calpain activation potentiates MMP activity by modulating TIMP balance and redox signaling, thereby coupling intracellular junctional injury to extracellular matrix degradation(37, 47)

A defining feature of the proteolytic storm in GM hemorrhage (GMH) is the emergence of neutrophil- and monocyte-derived proteases, which introduce an additional layer of injury distinct from developmental proteases. GMH tissue exhibits a shift from microglia-dominated to neutrophil-dominated inflammation(17). Neutrophils express high levels of elastase (ELANE), azurocidin-1 (AZU1), and CXCL16—proteases and chemokines capable of directly disrupting endothelial integrity(17). In vitro, AZU1 alone induces VE-cadherin loss and increases permeability in human microvessel models, while ELANE suppresses angiogenesis and accelerates junctional collapse. These immune-derived proteases act in addition to ongoing developmental angiogenic protease activity, amplifying junctional and basement-membrane injury altering the proteolytic environment of the germinal matrix.

The combination of intracellular and extracellular protease activation produces a nonlinear “inside-out” and “outside-in” collapse of the vascular wall. ADAM10 and calpains dismantle junctional complexes internally, while MMPs, cathepsins, AZU1, and ELANE erode the basement membrane externally(48, 49) (*see Figure 2*). Once these protease systems converge

in the context of developmental protease priming and immature GM vasculature, injury escalates non-linearly: inflammatory or hypoxic stimuli tolerated by mature cortical vessels precipitate catastrophic vascular collapse in the protease-primed GM(17). This calpain-centered paradigm unifies molecular observations across experimental and human GMH and identifies intracellular protease modulation as a tractable therapeutic entry point to modify the risk of GMH in preterm infants.

2.3 The Protease-Threshold Model: Mechanistic Basis for Timing, Localization, and Clinical Heterogeneity

The protease-threshold model provides a unifying mechanistic explanation for the distinctive timing of IVH, its selective localization to the GM, and the wide variation in susceptibility among infants of comparable gestational age. GMH occurs most frequently within the first 72 hours of life—a transitional period during which the newborn encounters an abrupt and simultaneous convergence of stimuli that activate proteolytic pathways. Early microbial colonization, even without overt infection, triggers transient bursts of TLR-dependent cytokine production(8, 50, 51). At the same time, intermittent hypoxia–ischemia, oxygenation fluctuations, and hemodynamic instability associated with mechanical ventilation amplify intracellular Ca^{2+} signaling and drive the activation of ADAM10, calpains, and MMPs(32, 33, 52). Experimental models and human-derived tissue analyses demonstrate that these inflammatory and hypoxic pathways interact synergistically: combined activation produces endothelial and basement-membrane injury far exceeding the additive effects of individual insults(17). In a vasculature already characterized by high developmental protease activity, even moderate postnatal stressors can raise the cumulative proteolytic load beyond the structural tolerance of the GM microvascular wall.

The anatomical specificity of hemorrhage reflects the unique structural and developmental features of the GM. GM vessels possess sparse pericyte coverage, incomplete astrocytic

ensheathment, and a thin, discontinuous basement membrane that is intrinsically more vulnerable to protease-mediated degradation than the more mature cortical vasculature(53, 54). In addition, the GM maintains high baseline protease activity due to its active angiogenesis(11, 55) and immune–vascular dependence that further contributes to the anatomical specificity of IVH in this region(17).

The susceptibility of individual infants to IVH varies widely—even among those of identical gestational age—because the protease threshold is not fixed. Instead, it fluctuates according to the magnitude of inflammatory activation, severity of hypoxic or metabolic stress, developmental stage of GM angiogenesis, and integrity of microglial–vascular interactions(17). Infants with heightened innate immune reactivity or early neutrophil infiltration display elevated levels of AZU1, ELANE, and CXCL16—immune-derived proteases that directly degrade VE-cadherin and basement-membrane components and thereby lower the threshold for vascular rupture (17, 56). Conversely, infants with preserved microglial–endothelial interactions maintain a higher structural tolerance and may withstand comparable postnatal stress without progressing to hemorrhage. This dynamic interplay among protease activation, immune reprogramming, and developmental stage accounts for the full clinical spectrum of GMH, from subclinical microhemorrhages to fulminant grade III–IV bleeding.

2.4 GMH as a Protease-Threshold Disorder

GMH is best conceptualized not as a passive consequence of structural immaturity but as a disorder of protease-threshold failure. The protease-threshold framework integrates developmental vascular vulnerability, dysregulated neonatal immunity, and inflammatory protease amplification into a unified causal model(17). It reconciles the developmental specificity of the germinal matrix, the narrow temporal window of postnatal risk, and the marked inter-individual heterogeneity in disease severity(17, 56). By reframing IVH as an active protease-driven process, the model identifies rational mechanistic priorities, including

preservation of immune–vascular support, modulation of innate immune activation, and targeted control of protease activity(38, 43, 57). It further establishes a conceptual basis for biomarker development to track evolving proteolytic state and guide precision-preventive strategies(17). Ultimately, effective prevention of IVH will require maintaining protease activity below the hemorrhagic threshold during the critical early postnatal period when developmental vulnerability and inflammatory amplification converge(17).

3. Loss of Immune Moderation and the Dysregulated Inflammatory Response

The transition from the sterile intrauterine environment to the microbially rich extrauterine world constitutes one of the most profound immunological challenges in human development. In term infants, this transition is buffered by a late-gestational program of immune moderation.

Swallowed amniotic fluid and early colostrum provide soluble TLR decoys, secretory IgA, lactoferrin, antimicrobial peptides, and anti-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-10 and TGF- β 25, which dampen neonatal innate immune activation and permit controlled engagement of microbial ligands during initial colonization while preventing excessive cytokine release or barrier injury(26, 27, 58). These systemic inflammatory signals provide the upstream trigger for the immune–vascular and proteolytic cascades described in Section 2

Preterm birth abruptly disrupts this developmental sequence. Rather than being simply immature, the preterm immune system exhibits a qualitatively dysregulated phenotype characterized by impaired host-defense capacity coexisting with exaggerated inflammatory responsiveness(14, 16, 59) Deficits in neutrophil chemotaxis, reduced antigen presentation, and diminished NK-cell cytotoxicity occur alongside heightened sensitivity to TLR2/TLR4 ligands and a bias toward pro-inflammatory signaling. As a result, physiologic early-life exposures—including microbial products, intermittent hypoxia, metabolic fluctuations, or mechanical stress—evoke disproportionate cytokine release dominated by IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-8, and TNF- α (58, 59). This exaggerated responsiveness reflects the absence of late-gestational immune buffering rather

than abnormal external stimuli. Consequently, normal microbial ligands encountered after preterm birth—from airway exposure, passage through the birth canal, early gut colonization, or low-level environmental products—are sufficient to trigger systemic cytokine and TLR-mediated activation(60-63).

This vulnerability is compounded by deficiencies in regulatory immune pathways. Infants born before 30 weeks of gestation exhibit decreased abundance and impaired suppressive function of regulatory T cells(64-66), resulting in inadequate IL-10 production and insufficient feedback inhibition of innate immune activation. In parallel, sterile insults such as hypoxia-ischemia, oxidative stress, and metabolic instability generate TLR-activating DAMPs, reinforcing cytokine cascades(65, 67-70). Common events in the life of a preterm infant—including apnea, hemodynamic instability, or routine handling—can therefore provoke sustained inflammatory responses(58).

Antenatal exposures further intensify this inflammatory predisposition. Chorioamnionitis, Ureaplasma colonization, and fetal inflammatory response syndrome prime the fetal innate immune system toward heightened cytokine release and independently increase the risk and severity of IVH across gestational ages(19, 71, 72). These prenatal inflammatory imprints lower the threshold for postnatal inflammatory activation and predispose the preterm infant to severe early-life cytokine surges.

During the first 48–72 hours, rapid microbial colonization, intermittent hypoxia, metabolic stress, and respiratory support converge on a hyperreactive innate immune system lacking adequate regulatory buffers(58, 59, 73). This early-life convergence produces a sustained systemic inflammatory tone characterized by elevated cytokines, oxidants, and circulating TLR ligands.

Circulating cytokines and DAMPs activate NF- κ B and p38 MAPK pathways in cerebral endothelial and perivascular cells, intensify oxidative stress, and reshape the periventricular

immune environment(74-76). In this setting, immune support programs that normally stabilize developing vasculature are diminished, while inflammatory myeloid recruitment is enhanced, creating the inflammatory input required for escalation toward vascular failure(40, 77).

4. Clinical and Translational Implications of the Protease-Threshold Model

Reconceptualizing intraventricular hemorrhage (IVH) as a disorder of protease-threshold failure—rather than a static consequence of structural immaturity—generates new avenues for prediction and prevention in neonatal care. In this framework, hemorrhage arises when the combined proteolytic load generated by developmental angiogenesis and postnatal inflammatory amplification surpasses the limited structural resilience of the germinal matrix (GM) vasculature. This perspective yields several translational implications.

4.1 Toward Mechanistically Informed Risk Stratification

Traditional risk stratification for GMH relies primarily on gestational age, birth weight, and indices of respiratory or hemodynamic instability(57). These variables capture vulnerability at the population level but offer little insight into the *biochemical progression* toward vascular failure. In the protease-threshold framework, the period of greatest diagnostic opportunity precedes overt hemorrhage by several hours to days: during the first 48–72 hours of postnatal life, inflammatory amplification progressively elevates proteolytic activity within the germinal matrix vasculature until the cumulative load surpasses the threshold for junctional and basement-membrane disruption(7, 19).

This creates a window in which circulating biomarkers—reflecting either junctional cleavage, protease activation, or upstream inflammatory drivers—may reveal that an infant is approaching

the hemorrhagic threshold. Junctional fragments such as soluble VE-cadherin or claudin-5, generated by ADAM10 or MMP activity, are detectable in peripheral blood in other settings of vascular injury(36, 78) and may serve as early indicators of endothelial destabilization. Similarly, activation-specific markers of MMP-9 or MMP-14, calpain-specific spectrin breakdown products, or cathepsin-derived ECM fragments could provide direct biochemical evidence of escalating protease activity(30, 79). Because obtaining cerebrospinal fluid is neither feasible nor ethical in clinically stable preterm infants, early screening must rely on minimally invasive samples—blood, heel-stick micro-samples, saliva, or urine—where many proteolytic and inflammatory markers are measurable using ultrasensitive platforms(80-82).

Upstream inflammatory signatures may also contribute to risk stratification. Elevated levels of IL-1 β , IL-6, TNF- α , or TLR-dependent transcriptional patterns are associated with exaggerated neonatal innate immune responses(83) and closely parallel the triggers that drive protease amplification. Integrating these mechanistic biomarkers into early postnatal surveillance could allow clinicians to distinguish infants who are trending toward threshold crossing from those whose vascular-immune environment remains stable despite similar demographic risk. In doing so, risk assessment would transition from a static clinical estimate to a dynamic evaluation of the evolving proteolytic state of the germinal matrix.

4.2 Restoring Immune Moderation and Modulating Proteolytic Load

Because the proteolytic storm is precipitated by loss of late-gestational immune buffering, strategies that partially restore this intrauterine moderation may attenuate postnatal inflammatory amplification(26, 27). Maternal colostrum—rich in secretory IgA, lactoferrin, antimicrobial peptides, IL-10, and TGF- β —has demonstrated capacity to reduce neonatal TLR responsiveness and limit excessive cytokine production(26, 58). Early provision of maternal colostrum, including oropharyngeal administration before full enteral feeding, may therefore help stabilize the inflammatory milieu during this narrow window of vulnerability(58).

Parallel strategies may focus on the protease systems themselves. Targeted modulation of MMPs, calpains, or ADAM10, augmentation of endogenous protease inhibitors such as TIMPs and cystatins, or stabilization of VE-cadherin adhesion complexes and intracellular Ca^{2+} homeostasis represent mechanistically rational interventions(28, 30, 38). Although any protease modulation must preserve physiological angiogenesis, the protease-threshold model provides a clear conceptual rationale for evaluating these approaches selectively in infants exhibiting biochemical evidence of junctional or basement-membrane degradation.

4.3 Implications for Long-Term Outcomes and PHH Prevention

Viewing GMH as a protease-driven barrier disorder situates hemorrhage within a larger continuum of periventricular injury. Proteolytic degradation of junctional complexes and basement membrane initiates downstream processes—ependymal disruption, ECM remodeling, periventricular gliosis, and altered CSF dynamics—that contribute to post-hemorrhagic hydrocephalus (PHH) and long-term neurodevelopmental impairment(1, 77). Interventions that prevent or attenuate the early proteolytic storm may therefore reduce not only the incidence and severity of IVH but also the likelihood of PHH and its associated sequelae.

This mechanistic understanding reinforces the importance of minimizing systemic inflammation in the NICU. Measures such as stringent infection control, cautious use of invasive procedures, optimization of ventilation to reduce hypoxia-ischemia cycles, and fostering physiologic microbial colonization all directly influence protease activation and vascular vulnerability(58, 83).

Given the convergence of inflammatory and hypoxic signaling on calpain activation, an important translational priority is to determine whether transient calpain inhibition can safely modulate proteolytic load during early-life inflammatory exposure and thereby prevent or mitigate acquired hydrocephalus without disrupting normal developmental angiogenesis.

4.4 Toward a Preventive Neurology for Preterm Infants

Taken together, the protease-threshold model integrates developmental neurobiology, neonatal immunology, and vascular pathology into a cohesive explanatory framework. It supports a shift from reactive management of hemorrhage to anticipatory preservation of proteolytic balance and vascular integrity. While substantial translational work remains, the model offers a mechanistically grounded path toward genuine prevention—an outcome long sought but rarely achievable in the care of extremely preterm infants.

5. Conclusions

IVH in preterm infants has long been framed as a passive consequence of vascular immaturity or hemodynamic instability. The synthesis presented here supports a more mechanistically integrated view: IVH arises from the pathological convergence of two normal developmental programs that become desynchronized by premature birth. The germinal matrix (GM) is intrinsically protease-active and structurally dynamic, reflecting its role in rapid angiogenesis and neurogenesis. Simultaneously, the preterm innate immune system—deprived of the late-gestational immunomodulatory inputs that normally buffer early microbial exposure—reacts to postnatal stimuli with exaggerated inflammatory activation. The protease threshold should not be interpreted as a fixed quantitative boundary, but as a dynamic balance between cumulative proteolytic activity and the evolving structural resilience of the germinal matrix vasculature

The intersection of these processes creates a state in which inflammatory cues amplify developmental proteolysis beyond its physiological limits, initiating cadherin cleavage, basement-membrane degradation, and progressive loss of microvascular integrity. This protease-threshold model provides a coherent explanation for the defining features of IVH: its precise localization to the GM, its narrow temporal window in the first days after birth, and its striking clinical heterogeneity even among infants of similar gestational age. Importantly, it

reframes GMH as a preventable biochemical failure state, not an unavoidable structural consequence of extreme prematurity.

This perspective suggests several translational directions. Biomarkers that reflect evolving proteolytic load—such as soluble junctional fragments, indicators of MMP or calpain activation, or signatures of heightened TLR signaling—may enable earlier risk stratification and dynamic prediction of threshold crossing. Likewise, interventions that restore elements of immune moderation or stabilize endothelial junctional complexes during the early postnatal period may reduce the incidence or severity of hemorrhage. More broadly, viewing GMH as a protease-driven barrier disorder links it to a wider spectrum of neurovascular pathologies in which inflammation and proteolytic amplification interact to destabilize developing or mature vascular beds.

By integrating developmental neurobiology, neonatal immunology, and protease-mediated vascular pathology, this framework offers a unified lens through which GMH can be mechanistically understood—and ultimately predicted, mitigated, and prevented.

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Author Contributions

L.C.-R. conceived the conceptual framework and drafted the manuscript.

A.L. contributed conceptual input and manuscript feedback.

B.W.H.† and M.M.† contributed clinical interpretation and critical revision.

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Declaration of Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data and Materials Availability

No new datasets were generated for this Perspective. Source data supporting the conclusions are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

AI statement

The authors used the artificial intelligence–based language model ChatGPT to assist with editing for clarity, organization, and grammar during manuscript preparation. All scientific content, interpretations, and conclusions were developed and verified by the authors.

References

1. Ballabh P, de Vries LS. White matter injury in infants with intraventricular haemorrhage: mechanisms and therapies. *Nature Reviews Neurology*. 2021; 17: 199-214.
2. Mukerji A, Shah V, Shah PS. Periventricular/intraventricular hemorrhage and neurodevelopmental outcomes: a meta-analysis. *Pediatrics*. 2015; 136: 1132-43.
3. Fernández-Muñoz B, Rosell-Valle C, Ferrari D, et al. Retrieval of germinal zone neural stem cells from the cerebrospinal fluid of premature infants with intraventricular hemorrhage. *Stem Cells Translational Medicine*. 2020; 9: 1085-101.
4. Piscopo BR, Sutherland AE, Malhotra A, et al. Pathogenesis of Preterm Intraventricular Haemorrhage. *Developmental Neuroscience*. 2025.
5. Braun A, Xu H, Hu F, et al. Paucity of pericytes in germinal matrix vasculature of premature infants. *Journal of neuroscience*. 2007; 27: 12012-24.
6. Egesa WI, Odoch S, Odong RJ, et al. Germinal Matrix-Intraventricular Hemorrhage: A Tale of Preterm Infants. *International journal of pediatrics*. 2021; 2021: 6622598.

7. Nagy Z, Obeidat M, Máté V, et al. Occurrence and time of onset of intraventricular hemorrhage in preterm neonates: a systematic review and meta-analysis of individual patient data. *JAMA pediatrics*. 2025.
8. Cai Y, Li X, Zhao X, et al. Risk assessment and early prediction of intraventricular hemorrhage in extremely preterm infants. *Scientific Reports*. 2025; 15: 17346.
9. Dave JM, Chakraborty R, Agyemang A, et al. Loss of TGF β -mediated repression of angiotensin-2 in pericytes underlies germinal matrix hemorrhage pathogenesis. *Stroke*. 2024; 55: 2340-52.
10. Yang D, Baumann JM, Sun Y-Y, et al. Overexpression of vascular endothelial growth factor in the germinal matrix induces neurovascular proteases and intraventricular hemorrhage. *Science translational medicine*. 2013; 5: 193ra90-93ra90.
11. van Hinsbergh VW, Engelse MA, Quax PH. Pericellular proteases in angiogenesis and vasculogenesis. *Arteriosclerosis, thrombosis, and vascular biology*. 2006; 26: 716-28.
12. Andreuzzi E, Colladel R, Pellicani R, et al. The angiostatic molecule Multimerin 2 is processed by MMP-9 to allow sprouting angiogenesis. *Matrix Biology*. 2017; 64: 40-53.
13. Lee CZ, Xue Z, Zhu Y, et al. Matrix metalloproteinase-9 inhibition attenuates vascular endothelial growth factor-induced intracerebral hemorrhage. *Stroke*. 2007; 38: 2563-68.
14. Sampah MES, Hackam DJ. Dysregulated mucosal immunity and associated pathogenesis in preterm neonates. *Frontiers in immunology*. 2020; 11: 899.
15. Twisselmann N, Pagel J, Künstner A, et al. Hyperoxia/Hypoxia exposure primes a sustained pro-inflammatory profile of preterm infant macrophages upon LPS stimulation. *Frontiers in immunology*. 2021; 12: 762789.
16. De Biasi S, Neroni A, Nasi M, et al. Healthy preterm newborns: altered innate immunity and impaired monocyte function. *European Journal of Immunology*. 2023; 53: 2250224.
17. Chen J, Crouch EE, Zawadzki ME, et al. Proinflammatory immune cells disrupt angiogenesis and promote germinal matrix hemorrhage in prenatal human brain. *Nature neuroscience*. 2024; 27: 2115-29.
18. Ballabh P, Xu H, Hu F, et al. Angiogenic inhibition reduces germinal matrix hemorrhage. *Nature medicine*. 2007; 13: 477-85.
19. Jung E, Romero R, Yeo L, et al. The fetal inflammatory response syndrome: the origins of a concept, pathophysiology, diagnosis, and obstetrical implications. *Seminars in Fetal and Neonatal Medicine: Elsevier*, 2020.
20. Oh KJ, Park JY, Lee J, et al. The combined exposure to intra-amniotic inflammation and neonatal respiratory distress syndrome increases the risk of intraventricular hemorrhage in preterm neonates. *Journal of perinatal medicine*. 2018; 46: 9-20.
21. Szpecht D, Wiak K, Braszak A, et al. Role of selected cytokines in the etiopathogenesis of intraventricular hemorrhage in preterm newborns. *Child's nervous system*. 2016; 32: 2097-103.
22. Dias ML, O'Connor KM, Dempsey EM, et al. Targeting the Toll-like receptor pathway as a therapeutic strategy for neonatal infection. *American Journal of Physiology-Regulatory, Integrative and Comparative Physiology*. 2021; 321: R879-R902.

23. Chen J, Choi JJ-Y, Lin P-Y, et al. Pathogenesis of germinal matrix hemorrhage: insights from single-cell transcriptomics. *Annual Review of Pathology: Mechanisms of Disease*. 2025; 20: 221-43.
24. Fields GB. Mechanisms of action of novel drugs targeting angiogenesis-promoting matrix metalloproteinases. *Frontiers in immunology*. 2019; 10: 1278.
25. Arroyo AG, Iruela-Arispe ML. Extracellular matrix, inflammation, and the angiogenic response. *Cardiovascular research*. 2010; 86: 226-35.
26. Levy O. Innate immunity of the newborn: basic mechanisms and clinical correlates. *Nature Reviews Immunology*. 2007; 7: 379-90.
27. Green ES, Arck PC. Pathogenesis of preterm birth: bidirectional inflammation in mother and fetus. *Seminars in immunopathology*: Springer, 2020.
28. Candelario-Jalil E, Yang Y, Rosenberg G. Diverse roles of matrix metalloproteinases and tissue inhibitors of metalloproteinases in neuroinflammation and cerebral ischemia. *Neuroscience*. 2009; 158: 983-94.
29. Vidak E, Javoršek U, Vizovišek M, et al. Cysteine cathepsins and their extracellular roles: shaping the microenvironment. *Cells*. 2019; 8: 264.
30. Rosenberg GA. Matrix metalloproteinases in neuroinflammation. *Glia*. 2002; 39: 279-91.
31. Dalal PJ, Muller WA, Sullivan DP. Endothelial cell calcium signaling during barrier function and inflammation. *The American journal of pathology*. 2020; 190: 535-42.
32. Curcio M, Salazar IL, Mele M, et al. Calpains and neuronal damage in the ischemic brain: The swiss knife in synaptic injury. *Progress in neurobiology*. 2016; 143: 1-35.
33. Blomgren K, Zhu C, Wang X, et al. Synergistic activation of caspase-3 by m-calpain after neonatal hypoxia-ischemia: a mechanism of “pathological apoptosis”? *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. 2001; 276: 10191-98.
34. Alluri H, Grimsley M, Shaji CA, et al. Attenuation of blood-brain barrier breakdown and hyperpermeability by calpain inhibition. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. 2016; 291: 26958-69.
35. Song L, Shi X, Kovacs L, et al. Calpain promotes LPS-induced lung endothelial barrier dysfunction via cleavage of talin. *American journal of respiratory cell and molecular biology*. 2023; 69: 678-88.
36. Dejana E, Vestweber D. The role of VE-cadherin in vascular morphogenesis and permeability control. *Progress in molecular biology and translational science*. 2013; 116: 119-44.
37. Aversa M, Bavestrello M, Cresta F, et al. Abnormal activation of calpain and protein kinase Ca promotes a constitutive release of matrix metalloproteinase 9 in peripheral blood mononuclear cells from cystic fibrosis patients. *Archives of biochemistry and biophysics*. 2016; 604: 103-12.
38. Zhang Y, Liu NM, Wang Y, et al. Endothelial cell calpain as a critical modulator of angiogenesis. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA)-Molecular Basis of Disease*. 2017; 1863: 1326-35.
39. Miyazaki T, Akasu R, Miyazaki A. Calpain proteolytic systems counteract endothelial cell adaptation to inflammatory environments. *Inflammation and Regeneration*. 2020; 40: 5.

40. Lembo C, Buonocore G, Perrone S. Oxidative stress in preterm newborns. *Antioxidants*. 2021; 10: 1672.
41. Defourny J, Peuckert C, Kullander K, et al. EphA4-ADAM10 interplay patterns the cochlear sensory epithelium through local disruption of adherens junctions. *Iscience*. 2019; 11: 246-57.
42. Perez M, Robbins ME, Revhaug C, et al. Oxygen radical disease in the newborn, revisited: Oxidative stress and disease in the newborn period. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine*. 2019; 142: 61-72.
43. Springer M, Burakgazi ZA, Domukhovska A, et al. HIF-1 α -Mediated Disruption of Cellular Junctions: The Impact of Hypoxia on the Tumor Microenvironment and Invasion. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 2025; 26: 5101.
44. Liu L, Yu J, Liu Y, et al. Hypoxia-driven angiogenesis and metabolic reprogramming in vascular tumors. *Frontiers in Cell and Developmental Biology*. 2025; 13: 1572909.
45. Zhao Y, Xing C, Deng Y, et al. HIF-1 α signaling: Essential roles in tumorigenesis and implications in targeted therapies. *Genes & diseases*. 2024; 11: 234-51.
46. Ming-Ming Z, Yi M, Meng T, et al. Hypoxia-induced upregulation of matrix metalloproteinase 9 increases basement membrane degradation by downregulating collagen type IV alpha 1 chain. *Physiological Research*. 2022; 71: 825.
47. Wang M, Kim SH, Monticone RE, et al. Matrix metalloproteinases promote arterial remodeling in aging, hypertension, and atherosclerosis. *Hypertension*. 2015; 65: 698-703.
48. Ivaldo C, Passalacqua M, Furfaro AL, et al. Oxidative stress-induced MMP-and γ -secretase-dependent VE-cadherin processing is modulated by the proteasome and BMP9/10. *Scientific Reports*. 2023; 13: 597.
49. Nishibori M, Wang D, Ousaka D, et al. High mobility group box-1 and blood-brain barrier disruption. *Cells*. 2020; 9: 2650.
50. Xiong P, Wei Y, Li L, et al. Prediction models for intraventricular hemorrhage in very preterm infants: a systematic review. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*. 2025; 13: 1605145.
51. Birkedal-Hansen H. Role of cytokines and inflammatory mediators in tissue destruction. *Journal of periodontal research*. 1993; 28: 500-10.
52. Hyatt HW, Ozdemir M, Bomkamp MP, et al. Activation of calpain contributes to mechanical ventilation-induced depression of protein synthesis in diaphragm muscle. *Cells*. 2022; 11: 1028.
53. Ballabh P. Pathogenesis and prevention of intraventricular hemorrhage. *Clinics in perinatology*. 2013; 41: 47.
54. Reddy PA, Sreenivasulu H, Shokrolahi M, et al. Navigating the complexities of intraventricular hemorrhage in preterm infants: an updated review. *Cureus*. 2023; 15.
55. Handsley MM, Edwards DR. Metalloproteinases and their inhibitors in tumor angiogenesis. *International journal of cancer*. 2005; 115: 849-60.
56. Liu H, Lessieur EM, Saadane A, et al. Neutrophil elastase contributes to the pathological vascular permeability characteristic of diabetic retinopathy. *Diabetologia*. 2019; 62: 2365-74.
57. Ballabh P. Intraventricular hemorrhage in premature infants: mechanism of disease. *Pediatric research*. 2010; 67: 1-8.

58. Humberg A, Fortmann I, Siller B, et al. Preterm birth and sustained inflammation: consequences for the neonate. *Seminars in Immunopathology*: Springer, 2020.
59. Melville JM, Moss TJ. The immune consequences of preterm birth. *Frontiers in neuroscience*. 2013; 7: 79.
60. Robertson SA, Hutchinson MR, Rice KC, et al. Targeting Toll-like receptor-4 to tackle preterm birth and fetal inflammatory injury. *Clinical & translational immunology*. 2020; 9: e1121.
61. Kennedy KM, Plagemann A, Sommer J, et al. Delivery mode, birth order, and sex impact neonatal microbial colonization. *Gut Microbes*. 2025; 17: 2491667.
62. Shao Y, Forster SC, Tsaliki E, et al. Stunted microbiota and opportunistic pathogen colonization in caesarean-section birth. *Nature*. 2019; 574: 117-21.
63. Pammi M, Lal CV, Wagner BD, et al. Airway microbiome and development of bronchopulmonary dysplasia in preterm infants: a systematic review. *The Journal of pediatrics*. 2019; 204: 126-33. e2.
64. Gomez-Lopez N, Arenas-Hernandez M, Romero R, et al. Regulatory T cells play a role in a subset of idiopathic preterm labor/birth and adverse neonatal outcomes. *Cell Reports*. 2020; 32.
65. Rueda CM, Wells CB, Gisslen T, et al. Effect of chorioamnionitis on regulatory T cells in moderate/late preterm neonates. *Human immunology*. 2015; 76: 65-73.
66. Zahran AM, Saad K, Abdel-Raheem YF, et al. Characterization of regulatory T cells in preterm and term infants. *Archivum Immunologiae et Therapiae Experimentalis*. 2019; 67: 49-54.
67. Schultz C, Temming P, Bucsky P, et al. Immature anti-inflammatory response in neonates. *Clinical & Experimental Immunology*. 2004; 135: 130-36.
68. Nadeau-Vallée M, Obari D, Palacios J, et al. Sterile inflammation and pregnancy complications: a review. *Reproduction*. 2016; 152: R277-R92.
69. Romero R, Chaiworapongsa T, Alpay Savasan Z, et al. Damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs) in preterm labor with intact membranes and preterm PROM: a study of the alarmin HMGB1. *The journal of maternal-fetal & neonatal medicine*. 2011; 24: 1444-55.
70. Padron JG, Saito Reis CA, Kendal-Wright CE. The role of danger associated molecular patterns in human fetal membrane weakening. *Frontiers in Physiology*. 2020; 11: 602.
71. Jain VG, Willis KA, Jobe A, et al. Chorioamnionitis and neonatal outcomes. *Pediatric research*. 2022; 91: 289-96.
72. Sabic D, Koenig JM. A perfect storm: fetal inflammation and the developing immune system. *Pediatric research*. 2020; 87: 319-26.
73. Hannawayya R, Puentes R, Mirzadzare N, et al. A multidimensional fecal microbial and inflammatory biomarker profiling in preterm and full-term neonates. *Pediatric Research*. 2025: 1-8.
74. Cindrova-Davies T, Spasic-Boskovic O, Jauniaux E, et al. Nuclear factor- κ B, p38, and stress-activated protein kinase mitogen-activated protein kinase signaling pathways regulate proinflammatory cytokines and apoptosis in human placental explants in

response to oxidative stress: effects of antioxidant vitamins. *The American journal of pathology*. 2007; 170: 1511-20.

75. Cao J, Wang Y, Lin Q, et al. IL-1 β stimulates ADAMTS9 expression and contributes to preterm prelabor rupture of membranes. *Cell Communication and Signaling*. 2025; 23: 127.

76. Radnaa E, Richardson L, Goldman B, et al. Stress signaler p38 mitogen-activated kinase activation: a cause for concern? *Clinical Science*. 2022; 136: 1591-614.

77. Ellison VJ, Mocatta TJ, Winterbourn CC, et al. The relationship of CSF and plasma cytokine levels to cerebral white matter injury in the premature newborn. *Pediatric research*. 2005; 57: 282-86.

78. Flemming S, Burkard N, Renschler M, et al. Soluble VE-cadherin is involved in endothelial barrier breakdown in systemic inflammation and sepsis. *Cardiovascular research*. 2015; 107: 32-44.

79. Siman R, Noszek JC, Kegerise C. Calpain I activation is specifically related to excitatory amino acid induction of hippocampal damage. *Journal of Neuroscience*. 1989; 9: 1579-90.

80. Ahmed S, Odumade OA, Van Zalm P, et al. Urine proteomics for noninvasive monitoring of biomarkers in bronchopulmonary dysplasia. *Neonatology*. 2022; 119: 193-203.

81. Molinero-Fernández Á, Moreno-Guzmán M, Arruza L, et al. Toward early diagnosis of late-onset sepsis in preterm neonates: dual magnetoimmunosensor for simultaneous procalcitonin and c-reactive protein determination in diagnosed clinical samples, *ACS Sens*. 4 (2019) 2117–2123.

82. Bellon Pizarro KN, Rolando JC, Maron JL, et al. Ultrasensitive detection of six sepsis-associated proteins in neonatal saliva. *npj Biosensing*. 2025; 2: 3.

83. Hagberg H, Gressens P, Mallard C. Inflammation during fetal and neonatal life: implications for neurologic and neuropsychiatric disease in children and adults. *Annals of neurology*. 2012; 71: 444-57.

Figure 1. Protease-threshold model of germinal matrix vessel collapse.

Top panels depict baseline vascular architecture in cortex (left) and germinal matrix (right) during peak germinal matrix angiogenesis (~24–32 gestational weeks). Cortical vessels exhibit continuous basement membrane, dense pericyte coverage, and stable microglial–vascular interactions, conferring high structural resilience. Germinal matrix vessels are angiogenic, display discontinuous basement membrane, sparse pericyte investment, and depend on vasculature-associated microglia for stabilization. Inflammatory triggers (e.g., hypoxia, infection, cytokines) induce immune activation in both compartments. In cortex, inflammatory amplification of protease activity produces increased endothelial permeability without vessel failure (physiological proteolysis). In the germinal matrix, inflammatory reprogramming reduces microglial vascular support and recruits neutrophils that release high-potency granule proteases (AZU1, ELANE), while endothelial ADAM family and calpain family proteases and extracellular MMP9 converge to degrade junctional and basement membrane substrates (proteolytic storm). The combined proteolytic load exceeds local vascular resilience, resulting in vessel rupture and hemorrhage. As, ADAM family; Cs, Calpain family; E, endothelial cell; M, microglia; N, neutrophil; P, pericyte; BM, basement membrane; GM, germinal matrix.

Figure 2 | Protease-resilience threshold model of germinal matrix vascular collapse in preterm IVH.

Conceptual framework illustrating how developmental protease priming and postnatal inflammatory amplification interact to determine the likelihood of germinal matrix hemorrhage across gestational age.

Central panel: Developmental landscape at birth. Vascular resilience $R(g)$ (blue) increases with advancing gestation as basement membrane deposition, pericyte coverage, and endothelial junctional maturation progress, while in-utero developmental protease activity $P_{dev}(g)$ (green) declines as germinal matrix angiogenesis resolves. Birth (red dashed lines) introduces a postnatal amplification term $A_{post}(g)$, reflecting inflammatory, hypoxic, and immune-derived protease activation following preterm delivery. The red boundary denotes the total proteolytic load $[P_{dev}(g) + A_{post}(g)]$, while the shaded region represents the incremental postnatal amplification acting on the developmental baseline, emphasizing the additive structure of the model.

Peripheral panels: Representative postnatal trajectories conditioned on birth at ~25, ~30, or ~35 gestational weeks (GW). Earlier gestational age is characterized by higher developmental protease priming and lower vascular resilience, such that a given magnitude of postnatal amplification is more likely to exceed the protease-resilience threshold. When the total proteolytic load surpasses vascular resilience $T(g) = [P_{dev}(g) + A_{post}(g)]/R(g) > 1$, the probability of junctional and basement-membrane failure is increased (purple-shaded regions); when $T(g) < 1$, vascular integrity is more likely to be preserved (green regions). Shaded areas and peak heights represent relative likelihood of threshold crossing rather than deterministic outcomes, highlighting that risk is highest during the early postnatal period and declines as inflammatory amplification resolves, with markedly lower risk in more mature infants.